

nuclei per hyphal cell; similar response of in vitro growth to temperature (see table); and disease development on maize inbred Cuba 257.

Responses of rice (R₆) and maize isolates (R₁) to carbendazim, benodanil, and thiabendazole were also similar. Two isolates, however, responded differently to thiophanate-M, dichloroline, and aureofungin. The rice isolate was more sensitive to dichloroline and less to thiophanate-M than the maize isolate, which failed to grow at the lowest thiophanate-M concentration (35 µg ai/ml). □

Comparison of maize and rice isolates of *R. solani* f. sp. *sasakii*, New Delhi, India.

Isolate	Origin	Nuclei/hyphal cell		Mode nuclear no.	Growth rate (mm/24 h)		Disease developed ^a on maize inbred Cuba 257 at			Mean virulence on 7 hosts ^c
		Range	Mean		25°C	30°C	25°C	30°C	35°C ^b	
R ₁	Maize	4-8	6.6	6	47	45	2.0	3.5	+ ^d	2.6
R ₂	Maize	3-13	6.6	6	37	37	1.5	1.5	+	2.0
R ₃	Maize	3-11	6.3	6	46	47	2.0	2.0	+ ^d	2.6
R ₄	Maize	3-13	6.3	6	27	35	2.0	3.5	+ ^d	2.9
R ₅	Rice	3-16	7.0	6	46	44	1.0	2.0	+	2.5
R ₆	Rice	3-9	5.4	6	47	47	3.0	3.0	+	2.7

^aDisease recorded on maize inbred Cuba 257 on 1-5 scale. ^b+ = growth in traces. ^cAverage of 4 readings each on 7 hosts. ^d production of infection cushions.

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Rice varietal reaction to leafhopper (LF) and yellow stem borer (YSB)

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We evaluated 6 promising 120- to 140-d rices for reaction to LF *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis* and YSB *Scirpophaga incertulas* in an adaptive research trial at Thozhudur, Thanjavur District, in 1983 thaladi when there was severe insect pressure.

Ten plants from nonreplicated plots of each variety were randomly chosen for scoring. LF reaction was based on the number of affected leaves in relation to the total leaves. YSB was scored based on the number of deadhearts as related to tillers/plant. Scoring was at flowering in Nov.

LF incidence ranged from 2 to 12%. Co 44, Pusa 169, AD9408, and Co 43 had resistant reaction. All varieties but Co 44 had fewer than 20% deadhearts, indicating YSB resistance (see table). □

Rice varietal reaction to LF and YSB incidence, Thozhudur, India.

Variety	Infestation (%)	
	LF ^a	YSB ^b
IET6262 (Pankaj/Vijaya)	11	11
AD9408 (IR20/IR8)	3	15
BS8 (IR36/Co 13)	12	8
Co 43 (Dasal/IR20)	8	18
Co 44 (ASD5/IR20)	2	23
Pusa 169 (IR28/P140)	2	19

^aBased on number of affected leaves in relation to total leaves. ^bBased on number of deadhearts as related to tillers/plant.

Rice resistance to brown planthopper (BPH) in the Solomon Islands

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About two and one-half annual irrigated rice crops are grown under mechanized cultivation on the Guadalcanal Plains of the Solomon Islands. The local BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* Stål population is highly virulent and resistant varieties only last 1-3 yr. We continually screen varieties for BPH resistance.

BG379-5 (BG96-3/Ptb 33) is believed to possess the Ptb 33 resistance gene and was first screened for BPH resistance in the 1980 International Rice Brown Planthopper Nursery. It was highly resistant,

Yield and resistance of BG379-5 to pests^a on the Guadalcanal Plains, Solomon Islands.

Seeded	Harvested	Resistance ^b to			Yield (t/ha)	Remarks
		BPH	LR	ShB		
29 Jul 83	28 Nov 83	1.5	1.0	4.0	7.3	Heavy ShB incidence
11 Aug	12 Dec	1.0	1.0	—	4.6	Stunted and yellowing
20 Oct	16 Feb 84	2.0	1.0	2	3.8	Moderate army worm damage
29 Oct	5 Mar	1.4	1.0	3	5.3	—
26 Nov	28 Mar	1.4	1.0	—	6.2	Moderate brown spot incidence
17 Dec	18 Apr	3.0	1.5	5.3	4.8	Heavy army worm attack
20 Jan 84	18 May	4.5	1.0	2	5.0	—
10 Feb	7 Jun	7.3	1.0	—	4.0	60% hopperburned
19 Mar	16 Jul	7.0	1.0	—	4.9	—
6 Apr	21 Jul	6.0	1.0	—	3.4	—

^a LR = leafroller, ShB = sheath blight. ^bRated according to the *Standard evaluation system for rice*: 1 = most resistant, 9 = most susceptible.

scoring 1 on the 1-9 IRRI *Standard evaluation system for rice* and yielded 7-8 t/ha. It was released for commercial use on the Solomon Islands in 1982 and until recently has shown BPH resistance.

To monitor BG379-5 performance, we conducted yield trials from Jul 1973 to Jul 1984. Seeds were planted monthly in randomly chosen 3- × 5-m plots with 4 replications. Thirty, 40, and 40 kg N/ha

was applied at 25-30, 45-55, and 70-75 d after seeding (DS).

We monitored BPH and populations of pests such as seed shrimp *Chrissia* sp. and *Cypris* sp., leaf miner *Hydrellia griseola* Fallen, armyworms *Mythimna separata* Walker and *Spodoptera exempta* Walker, and leafroller *Marasmia exigua*. At early rice growth, furadan 10G, fenitrothion

50% EC, and parathion 50% EC were applied at -2, +10-15, and +30-45 DS to control seed shrimp, leaf miner, and armyworm. BPMC 50% EC and fenitrothion/parathion were applied at 25-d intervals 45 DS to control BPH, armyworm, and leafroller. With regular insecticide application, BG379-5 maintained high BPH resistance until Apr 1984,

after which it was heavily attacked by BPH, which occasionally caused hopperburn. In Jun 1984, 60% hopperburn was observed (see table).

Gradually reduced resistance has been typical of several resistant varieties during the last 10 yr. Leafroller and armyworm have occasionally reduced yields, but not seriously. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DEEP WATER

Effect of fertilizers on yield and yield components of medium deep water rice culture in northern Nigeria

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We evaluated the effect of NPK on yield and yield components of a new deep water rice, BKN6986-38-1, at the RRS, Birnin Kebbi, in 1983. BKN6986-38-1 matures 3-4 wk earlier and has 34% higher average yield and better grain appearance than deep water variety FARO 14.

Treatments were 0, 35, or 70 kg/ha each of N, P, and K in 3³ factorial arrangement in a randomized complete block design with 4 replications. Rice was planted in 3- × 5-m plots on an annually flooded clay soil that had been planted to rice for several years.

One-half N and all P and K were incorporated in wet soil with a hoe, 1 d before transplanting. The remaining N was drilled between rows 21 d after transplanting. NPK sources were ammonium sulfate, single superphosphate, and potassium chloride.

Three-week-old BKN6986-38-1 seedlings were transplanted at 25- × 30-cm spacing at 1 seedling/hill on 12 Aug, which was a late planting. Seedlings were irrigated and supplemental irrigation was applied as needed. The plots were flooded the 3d wk of Sep reaching a depth of 33 cm. The floodwater receded 1 mo later. The crop matured 15 Nov.

There was a highly significant yield

Effect of NPK fertilizers on grain yield and yield components of deep water rice BKN6986-38-1, Birnin Kebbi, Nigeria, 1983.

Fertilizer dose (kg/ha) N - P - K	Grain yield (t/ha)	Panicles/m ²	Field grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)
0 - 0 - 0	1.7	133	107	28
0 - 0 - 35	1.3	75	97	27
0 - 0 - 70	2.1	138	90	26
0 - 35 - 0	2.3	149	124	29
0 - 35 - 35	3.0	173	112	29
0 - 35 - 70	1.7	115	112	28
0 - 70 - 0	2.1	133	122	27
0 - 70 - 35	2.5	122	108	27
0 - 70 - 70	1.8	122	101	26
35 - 0 - 0	3.0	153	99	28
35 - 0 - 35	2.6	171	109	30
35 - 0 - 70	2.4	151	106	26
35 - 35 - 0	2.8	164	82	28
35 - 35 - 35	3.7	175	109	28
35 - 35 - 70	2.9	155	102	28
35 - 70 - 0	3.3	169	132	29
35 - 70 - 35	2.8	167	101	30
35 - 70 - 70	2.7	164	126	29
70 - 0 - 0	3.5	209	100	27
70 - 0 - 35	3.4	215	119	29
70 - 0 - 70	3.1	191	106	30
70 - 35 - 0	3.7	189	119	28
70 - 35 - 35	3.7	217	109	30
70 - 35 - 70	3.5	191	111	29
70 - 70 - 0	3.3	186	112	29
70 - 70 - 35	3.3	218	113	30
70 - 70 - 70	3.3	186	129	30

LSD for N** at 5%	0.3 t/ha	13.2/m ²	NS N** (at 5% 0.6 g	
1%	0.4 t/ha	17.6/m ²	K** (at 1% 0.8 g	
LSD for P* at 5%	0.3 t/ha		NP** (at 5% 1.02 g	
			NK** (at 1% 1.40 g	
Coefficient of variability	23.7%	17.1%	20.8%	4.4%

*Means significantly differ at 5% level. **Means significantly differ at 1% level. NS Means are not significantly different.

increase with 35 kg N/ha and a further significant increase with 70 kg N/ha (see table). Grain yield significantly increased with 35 kg P/ha, but had no response to higher application. K at 35 kg/ha did not influence yield. At higher doses, it decreased yield but improved 1,000-grain

weight. The interactions N × P, N × K, and N × P × K did not significantly affect grain yield.

There was a linear increase in panicles/m² with N application, but the number of filled grains was not significantly affected. □